

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIRECT AND DIRECT TRANSLATION INTO UZBEKI

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Abstract: In this article, there are comments on the scientific-theoretical and comparative analysis of direct and indirect translation from a foreign language to Uzbek in linguistics.

Key words: Linguistics, foreign language, translator, folk culture, literature, science, dictionary, language tools.

Translation and interpreting is one of the oldest creative fields that have been forming in the history and culture of the peoples of the world for centuries. Generations of people who have been living in different continents and regions of the earth for several thousand years have shown their creative passions, interests, opportunities and interests through the medium of translation. He turned it into a means of international communication, which he always used effectively. Through translation and translators, the peoples of mankind became aware of each other and communicated with each other. At the same time, he gradually developed and launched such fields as trade, handicrafts, housing, road construction, agriculture, and armaments. People learned from each other how to live a comfortable and safe life, showed each other the way, took examples from each other and showed each other the attractive aspects of various cultures.

Translation is a complex yet important process. People establish mutual relations with the help of translation. Among them can be political, economic, social, cultural relations, including literary relations, which occupy a high place in the development of the nation. Translation connects countries and develops literature, art, and economy. No nation develops on its own, it is helped by discoveries and innovations created in different countries, of course, translation takes an active part in this process. Translation of samples of foreign literature is also very important in this respect, and it is done in different ways. We can say indirect and direct translations from them.

Indirect translation is a translation from the original into one language, and then into another language (through the intermediate language). An indirect translation tool can be successful or unsuccessful depending on the translated text. Because there are many problems in literary translation, the first of which is the adequacy of the translation and, at the same time, the ability to feel the

atmosphere. The reader who reads the translation should be able to feel everything that the reader who read the original felt. Only then the translator will have done his job. It is also important to convey the author's style in translation. Because the author's signature and uniqueness lies in the work. If the translator cannot deliver these, the author's style will be lost and it will not come out like the original. These again have a strong influence on the process of translation into a second language, and the original feeling can be lost.

Literature is the art of words, so the translation of works of art deserves the same definition. Knowing the language and its grammar is not enough for artistic translation. To translate a work of art, the translator must have talent and penmanship. That is why poets and writers are mainly involved in the translation of literary works. After all, it is not enough to simply translate the words of the work, one should also be aware of the culture, customs, traditions, and peculiarities of the people who are the owners of the language being translated.

The subject of translation theory is closely related to the practice of translation, translation works, translation processes, the role of the translator, the history of translation and the language based on their study, reflects and summarizes the laws and guidelines of translation. The theory of translation scientifically and critically examines views, points of view, observations, and various experiences related to the wide living practice of translation, describes the rules and principles of translation, the boundaries and norms of the field. In this sense, translation theory and translation studies (like literary theory and literary studies) are very close and complementary concepts. It should only be remembered that translation studies also includes translation criticism, which, if it is unnecessary, is the linguist of translation studies and, at the same time, its vanguard.

The difference between languages is usually explained by the fact that certain concepts, events, and traditions that exist in the material life of the same nation do not occur in the lifestyle of the second nation, and because of this, their names do not naturally exist in the language of the same nation. In addition, some pairs of two languages that are in the relationship of lexical equivalence may differ from each other in some features. This situation hinders their mutual exchange in translation while determining the national character of language units.

In the scientific literature, there is no single opinion about the need to interpret the lexical units that express the concepts of people's life by means of the tried

and tested methods of translation. Due to the creative process of translation, such an idea is sometimes impossible to meet. However, the described scientific and critical opinions enrich the translator's imagination about how he should act in certain cases, help him to solve the various random knots that can be allowed in practice, and solve the problem of skillfully overcoming practical problems. creates.

It is one of the most responsible and extremely difficult issues of such a complex problem as the adequate interpretation of such words, which mean the concepts of people's life, in the translation, as well as the complete delivery of the national characteristics of the original copy to the reader. After all, in such a case, it is a daily task for the translator to fully understand the concepts, things and events that are unfamiliar to his people, and consequently, the names of which do not exist in the language, to the owners of the translated language.

Nowadays, the Uzbek language has become one of the rich and powerful languages of the world, and one of the factors that has brought it to this level is that most of the linguistic tools in the dictionary, which represent the life concepts of other peoples, have been adopted by the translation method, and express any subtle thoughts of the language. because he overestimated his ability to receive.

But sometimes the translation method is abused by some translators. They are devoid of national color and use this tool to interpret linguistic tools that have similar meaning and function in the translated language, which makes it difficult for the reader to understand the expressed idea. For example, in the translation of a number of works from Uzbek to Russian, many non-national words such as "rais", "hammam", "aka", "yor", "eshshak" are left untranslated, considering them to be of a national nature. indicates their imagination.

A witness to the fact that the characters of works translated from Uzbek to English or dubbed films sometimes greet each other with "Hello", "Hello", "Good morning", "Good afternoon", "Good night" we will be Although the Uzbek forms "salam" and "assalamo alykum" are devoid of any nationality, they are similar speech forms to these Russian means of expression in terms of meaning and function.

It is self-evident that only words expressing the way of life of a certain people are transferred to the languages of peoples who do not have such concepts in their original form without translation, thus the national color of the author's text is adequately interpreted in the translation. For example, "tahmon", "hurjin", "pilov", "ketmon", "paranji", "supa" are the means of expression that

are unique to the Uzbek way of life. Untranslated, while preserving the national character of the original, provides an opportunity to expand the vocabulary of translated languages.

It is known that people's names are translated mainly by translation. The pronunciation of each name in the original version in most cases indicates to which nation it belongs. However, the special pronunciation of some letters in the original language in the translated language can cause the pronunciation of the name to be drastically different from the original name. Because of this, experienced artists do not blindly transliterate people's names all the time, but also pay attention to the aspects of their reading and pronunciation in the translated language, as a result of which transliteration and transcription are mixed.

In conclusion, it should be noted that translation had a great impact on the development of literature, art and science in the world civilization. Since ancient times, translation has been considered a secondary profession in the eyes of people, but it has been used in all aspects of life. We will be able to see scientific-theoretical and comparative analyzes of direct and indirect translations into Uzbek as examples in different directions. One of the main tasks of the translator is to reveal the scientific features and comparative analysis of the translated works in the work of the translator.

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